

FUNDAMENTALS OF DEDUCTION AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTS OF THE FACULTY OF PHARMACY

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Abstract

The article substantiates the role of using the basics of deduction among medical students of the Faculty of Pharmacy. The use of this method allows to generalize the acquired knowledge and form the correct conclusion. The main goal is to assess the basics of deduction among medical students (namely, the Faculty of Pharmacy) based on a literature review. To solve the set goal and tasks, the basis of the first stage of the research is an assessment of the role of deduction in the educational process, its advantages and disadvantages by studying the literature, and the second stage is an assessment of the essence of the concept of "personality", ways of influencing its development.

It has been established that the role of deduction (deductive method) among medical students is in the formation of correct clinical and pharmaceutical thinking, and a correctly presented pedagogical approach will allow obtaining the desired result among students. It has been established that the logic of the educational process, systematization, and orientation of the topic by the teacher will attract the attention of each student and interest him in analyzing the topic. The use of deduction while studying at a medical university will allow to influence the already formed personality of the student and develop a "constructive" type of personality orientation in him. Therefore, this method is an actual issue today.

Keywords. Deduction, teacher, student, learning, personality, personality orientation, typology.

Introduction.

As you know, in Ukraine, scientists described deduction in different directions (specialties). The basics of the development of deduction were highlighted in his articles by Vinnytsia scientist Oleg Khoma [5]. I.E. Andryushchenko, V.I. Kolesnik described the role of the deductive method in strategic planning at enterprises. They recognized that when using this method, a "true conclusion" will always be obtained [1]. Maxim Lutfullin highlighted the role of deduction in the history of mathematics and mathematics education in his collections. He described the influence of induction and deduction on the development of mathematical analysis [4].

M.F. Shklyar described the basics of deduction from different points of view of personal development of a person, where logic considers deduction as a conclusion, and human psychology - the development and violation of deductive reasoning. This analysis leads to the "structure of mental activity" [5].

V.V. Yagupov noted that deduction helps teachers to determine the correctness of the path and method of learning, innovatively and creatively organize training sessions and effectively solve didactic tasks [6].

Deductive method research was offered for pedagogical purposes in III and IV accreditation level institutions.

S.S. In her works, Vitvytska highlighted the main approaches to the pedagogical training of specialists of the highest qualification level and noted that the use of the basics of deduction in pedagogical theory expands the development of professional personal qualities, which ensures success and productivity in the performance of tasks of an innovative nature [2].

According to the given literature data, it is known that the deductive method has been used repeatedly in the mathematical, social, pedagogical and economic spheres, however, there is little data on the application of this method in the medical field. Therefore, the mentioned question is certainly relevant today.

The main goal is to assess the basics of deduction among medical students (namely, the Faculty of Pharmacy) based on a literature review.

Justification

To solve the set goal, we have proposed two stages of highlighting this problem.

The basis of the first stage of the research is the assessment of the role of deduction in the educational process, its advantages and disadvantages by studying the literature. It is the identification of the advantages and disadvantages of the deductive method that allows teachers to pay attention to the quality of the teaching material and the importance of deduction during the educational process. Taking into account the various

methods of pedagogical theory, induction and deduction are among the methods that allow in the educational process to "coordinate" the medical student in the right direction to form the correct conclusion. This method combines various techniques that stimulate the student to critical thinking, which is indispensable in the medical field. Therefore, such a stage is necessary to solve the above-mentioned issues.

Assessment of the essence of the concept of "personality", ways of influencing its development - the basis of the deductive method. A medical student of the Faculty of Pharmacy is a person with established goals both in life and in scientific and career paths. The specified method will help highlight problematic issues in personality development - the influence of society, science, and education on the typology of each student and the ways of his perception. The combination of these questions is the basis for forming a conclusion.

Results and discussion.

Every teacher in his scientific education uses induction along with deduction. The dialectic of induction and deduction is a very important point in the process of the movement of thought from ignorance to knowledge [7].

Deduction is part of general theoretical research and is based on knowledge of facts and phenomena on the basis of generally accepted laws and rules. In medicine, without specification (laboratory, instrumental, and anamnestic data) it is impossible to make a correct conclusion (diagnosis) and, especially, to choose the right treatment or emergency drugs. Knowing the basis of the disease and its course, taking into account concomitant pathologies, only the pharmacist can evaluate the pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of this drug and recommend it for this or that disease. The basis of deduction enables a medical student to quickly make a preliminary diagnosis. But correct diagnosis requires not only skill and reasoning, but also knowledge that a medical student acquires during the educational process. That is, there are three directions in which deduction "works". This is a big "baggage" of knowledge, thinking and conclusion.

Jonathan Street Evans described the application of the "uncertain deduction" method and the binary paradigm in his works [8]. However, this method is impractical in the use of analysis of medical topics and the practical application of the acquired knowledge, as there is no clarity in the researched direction, which may cause an incorrect conclusion. "Indefinite deduction" confirmed its value through probability theories, which are built on some clear provisions that allow specifying the researched and presenting a probable conclusion [9].

The deductive method using abstract thematic modeling and identification technology will make it possible to understand and recognize the received data and formulate the correct conclusion [10].

As you know, based on the results of research by I.A. Kozhushko knows that the use of the deductive method in pedagogical education has a motivational role and, at the same time, allows to activate the mental activity of students. [3].

However, in addition to the proper presentation of educational material, the assimilation of the level of knowledge among medical students is different, taking into account the psychological characteristics of the individual and his comprehensive development (orientation not only in one specialized direction).

Before the student period, a person possesses a set of social roles formed under the influence of parents and the environment (society, including the teacher)). Therefore, when entering educational institutions, a novice student has a formed temperament, abilities, character and personality orientation. In this case, the influence of the pedagogical theory of higher education institutions should be individual, complex (application of several methods at the same time), interesting and relaxed (so that the student himself shows interest in analyzing the medical topic).

Different personality types are found among medical students, but the personality of the student, the type of thinking also affects the assessment of the patient's condition and the correct selection of the drug.

The basis of the student's typology is scientific and social activity, attitude to learning, general cultural awareness and a sense of collectivism.

A great role in the "art" of assimilation of knowledge, abilities, and skills belongs to the mastery of the teacher, his pedagogical training, the presentation of the material and its delivery to each medical student. The ability to differentiate between pathological conditions is the key to successful generalization and deduction.

"Deductive thinking" is formed with the correct presentation of educational material to students and systematicity. Each seminar and practical session has its own time "gradation" and scheme of its implementation. In higher educational institutions, the schematic presentation of the class takes place according to the Bologna process of learning in a certain sequence. That is, at the beginning of the lesson, the teacher checks the initial level of knowledge of the material. Next, a collective analysis of the topic - consideration of issues related to the explanation of the pathogenetic features of the disease, the clinical picture, the course of the disease, the evaluation of the obtained examination results, comparative characteristics with other diseases, the diagnosis (correct formulation according to the classifications), justification of methods and treatment. Next is the practical part, where each student puts the acquired knowledge into practice. The final stage is the verification of the final level of knowledge. It is during the period of theoretical and practical analysis of the educational material that the teacher's individual approach to the presentation of the material and deductive methods are used for better understanding and assimilation of knowledge.

The presentation of the material is always carried out according to such criteria as conceptuality, process logic, systematicity, controllability, efficiency, reproducibility.

Conceptuality is based on a concept containing philosophical, psychological, didactic and socially based educational goals. The logic of the process is the relationship of knowledge from different subjects,

which allows us to assume a preliminary conclusion about the course and pathogenesis of the disease. Systematicity allows you to clearly establish the development of the disease in stages, which will allow you to effectively and maximally achieve the planned result in the selection of drugs and treatment.

In this case, the application of the deductive method during the period of study and the practical part of employment will allow a medical student of the pharmaceutical field to assess his educational opportunities, increase his thinking "threshold", increase the amount of knowledge and learn to substantiate the obtained results and draw correct conclusions. This is the current issue today.

Conclusions and prospects for further research.

Conclusion. The use of deduction enables a medical student to make a correct medical conclusion (diagnosis) and assess the patient's condition and choose the drug correctly and effectively.

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